

Agronomy of Wild Asparagus Cultivation

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Asparagus acutifolius L.

Asparagus acutifolius L. is a spontaneous evergreen shrub of the family Liliaceae, common in the Mediterranean region. The species inhabits the Mediterranean *macchia* and the wood margins at different elevations, its requirements in nutrients and water being frugal. Due to the adaptability to harsh environments, this species is adequate for cultivation in marginal areas, in both arable lands and agroforestry systems.

Equipped with a vigorous rhizome system the wild asparagus is suitable to be cultivated in a variety of soil types, enclosing the skeleton rich soils on calcareous substrates. However, the species colonises also other kinds of soils, enclosed the volcanic ones at low elevations.

Recent experiments at the ARSIAL agronomic station of Alvito (Comino valley, FR, Italy) provide basic agrotechnical results for the wild asparagus cultivation in open field: ploughing at 50 cm depth; 0.9 trees/ha of sheep manure; preparation of the seeding bed with rotary tiller; no use of mineral fertilisers and herbicides.

The highest production on area basis is obtained with a plant density of 4 plants per m² and drip irrigation guarantees a second spear harvest in autumn, although less relevant than the spring one. Considering the spring harvest, the productivity comparing trials over 4 years ranges in between 1 and 1.6 trees/ha per year. The autumn harvest, obtained by clear cutting of the plants, is around 0.3 trees/ha. However, doubts exist about the weakening of the plantation over time, due to this forcing of the spears production.

The economic value of the wild spears is much higher than that of the cultivated species (*A. officinalis*), particularly on the short value chain eventually present on the specific territory. However, due to its frugality, the wild asparagus is specifically interesting in marginal areas for intercropping within orchards or groves, for instance in the ancient olive groves in order to increase their limited remunerability.

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